

BBSRC

Data management plan required?	Yes. Mandatory for all research grant applications as a separate attachment.
RDM policy Link	http://bbsrc.ukri.org/documents/data-sharing-policy-pdf/
Definition of data	Not specified
Length of data management plan	Maximum of 1 side of A4.
DMP template/ requirements	Data areas and type (volume, type, content, measurements, models, records, images), standards and methodologies, relationship to other data available, further intended use, methods for data sharing, restrictions on data sharing, format of final data set. Data sharing should be monitored and information submitted into ResearchFish, which will allow monitoring of proposed DMP.
Required data repository	Recommended. BBSRC supports/ funds a number of repositories, databases. Preferable to using existing infrastructure.
Time for data release	No later than published research (Ideally 3 years)
Time for long-term storage of data	10 years after the end of the research project grant
Costings	Funding can be requested as part of the application. This can include support for staff, storage and network capabilities. Other schemes allow funds to be requested for: Development of standards and software which enable data sharing; Community resources to facilitate data sharing within specific communities; Data sharing activities; Information and guidance to applicants Support for relevant training activities.
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Comments	Part of UKRI. Data should be accompanied by appropriate metadata to provide secondary users with sufficient information on the data to prevent misuse, misinterpretation/ confusion.

Documents used:BBSRC Data sharing policy <http://bbsrc.ukri.org/documents/data-sharing-policy-pdf/>BBSRC data management plan <https://bbsrc.ukri.org/funding/apply/application-guidance/data-management/>**Accessed:** May 2018